

PHILOSOPHICAL IDEAS AND THEIR CLASSIFICATION IN THE EMIRATE OF BUKHARA AT THE BEGINNING OF THE 20TH CENTURY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10443991>

Abstract. This article provides information about a number of philosophical ideas and their classification that prevailed in Central Asia, especially in the Emirate of Bukhara, at the beginning of the 20th century. Special attention is paid to the research of the scientific heritage of our ancestors who lived and created during this period, and in particular, attention is paid to its place in the education of young people. In addition to these, the purpose and activity of the philosophy of the 20th century, its importance and development are highlighted.

Key words. Bukhara Emirate, moderns, Ahmad Danish, Abdurauf Fitrat, Fayzulla Khojaye, Usmonkhujja Pulathujayev, idea, emirs, reform, spirituality, social life.

Introduction

In the first quarter of the 20th century, all layers of the population of Bukhara Emirate experienced a rich and multifaceted spiritual and cultural life. The material foundations of the spiritual and cultural life in the Bukhara state and its social roots are formed by the strengthening of the country's economy and the astrologers and changes in the structure of the population. Thus, economic, social and cultural changes in a number of countries of the world had a positive effect to a certain extent. The spiritual-scientific environment in the country, especially in Bukhara, with its content, the rise of theological-secular, science-enlightenment literature to a high level, crafts, jewelry, trade, commerce, and architectural works are quite for their time. is distinguished by its high level of organization. On this ground, by the 20th century, a growing social movement was born in the country. The enlightenment, culture, and spirituality of the people of Bukhara, which developed until the overthrow of the emir's power, are gathered by the human values, religious-educational, scientific-ethical, creative arts and traditions that have been formed over the centuries. Indisi has created rich material written heritages. Spirituality was also characterized by loyalty to one's homeland, language, its history, deep respect, respect for religious people, scholars, meritorious teachers, and striving for creativity.

Results

In the indicated period, that is, at the beginning of the 20th century, the Bukhara Emirate was ruled by Amir Muzaffar Khan's son Amir Abdulahad (1885-1910) and his heir Amir Said Olim Khan. They will inherit the throne of Bukhara, which is completely dependent on Russia. They could not solve a case by themselves. In the first years of Amir Abdulahad's rule, there were protests against him in a number of regions. These speeches of the people are brutally suppressed. However, it should be said that according to the documents of 1886-1887, Amir Abdulahad Khan issued a decree on the official release of slaves and maidservants. After his death in 1910, the throne passed to his son Olim Khan (1910-1920). During his rule,

Amir Olimkhan also carried out a number of useful works for the benefit of the people. He himself writes about it as follows: "After I ascended the throne, I issued an order to exempt my country from paying one year's tribute to this servant. I built a mosque for worship in my name near the Bukharai Sharif arch, in the place called Baloyi Pool. On the lower side of the Bukhara tower, on the inside of the market, I built a madrasa called Dar-ul-ulum - House of Knowledge in my name: I appointed teachers to teach various sciences. The expenses, salary and clothing of the students living in this madrasa were determined by me, and I appointed a nazir for it; I would deliver their food, wages and clothes at a certain time. I made a lot of efforts to improve the market and roads, in three years the country of Bukhara became much more prosperous..."

Ahmad Donish was one of the notable representatives of the advanced social thought of the peoples of Central Asia at that time, he was a doctor, poet, musician, artist, astrologer, scientist and calligrapher. Ahmad Donish is considered to be the founder of the enlightenment movement. As a historian actively involved in the political affairs of his country, Ahmad Donish takes the history of the rule of the Mangit emirs of Bukhara under sharp and cruel satire in his work. In the work "Risolai historikia" or "History of the Kingdom of Mangitiya" he shed light on many historical events in a new way. It tells a brief story about the last years of the reign of Emir Daniyal and the reign of three emirs - Shahrurad, Haydar and Nasrullah. Ahmad Donish broke the old traditions of official history, boldly announced his new political beliefs and founded a new progressive direction in the social thought of his time. He knew that the main strength of the progressive movement in the country is to enlighten the people. He criticized the rule of the emir of Bukhara, the luxurious life of the wealthy classes and the high priest. "Every person should work and live on the money he earns," said Ahmad Donish. In his works, he encouraged to study and acquire knowledge.

Discussion

The names of Abdurauf Fitrat, Fayzulla Khojaev, Usmonkhoja Polathojaev, Abdulvahid Burkhanov, Sadriddin Ainiy, Abudulkadir Mukhiddinov are among the activists of the Jadidist movement in Bukhara. Mirza Sirojiddin Hakim Bukhari has a special role in the emergence of the reform movement in Bukhara Emirate. Having traveled the world and seen the development in developed countries with his own eyes, Mirza Sirojiddin expressed his reaction to the problems of Bukhara society and presented his suggestions for their elimination. Mirzo Sirojiddin, who has excellent religious and worldly knowledge and can speak Russian and French languages, started his first trip to foreign countries at the age of 25. His reason for going on a trip was "... to see the prosperity and ruins of the world, to be aware of the progress of science and art, to present all his experiences and information to his religious and fellow citizens about his travels, and to travel the people to inform about the benefits.

As one of the organizers of Bukhara jadids, Abdurauf Fitrat fought hard to make the people enjoy enlightenment and culture. From 1915, he headed the left wing of the "Young Bukhara" movement. The poet, who dreams of seeing his motherland free and free, wrote a poem and four poems called "The Sorrow of the Country", in which he sings the idea of the struggle for freedom. In these paintings, the artist portrays Turkestan in the image of a humiliated and humiliated Mother, and in order to free Mother from the oppressors, she includes people like Amir Temur.

Usmonkhoja Polathojayev is a prominent representative of the Jadidist movement in Bukhara, a well-known state and public figure. His father, Kori Polathoja, was a merchant from Bukhara. He received his primary education at a madrasa in Bukhara and founded one of the first modern schools. There is very little information about Usmonkhoja's life and activities between 1898 and 1910. During these years, Usmonkhoja was a member and one of the leaders of the Jadidist movement, which spread throughout Turkestan. Although the Jadidism movement initially initiated fundamental changes in education, it later turned into a political movement and even a political party.

Conclusion

The development path of independence created wide opportunities for the development of science in our country. Fundamental changes took place in philosophy, as in all branches of science. After all, philosophy, which has the most ancient history of development, embodies the socio-political views of different eras and forms an understanding of the essence of events and phenomena, not only understanding, but also reacting to them. As long as this is the case, today it is important to further develop philosophy, to arm the young generation with philosophical worldview and philosophical knowledge based on the achievements of modern science.

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